

Evaluating the Effectiveness of CSPM Tools in Detecting Cloud Misconfigurations

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Abstract—Despite heavy adoption of the cloud, misconfigurations are often overlooked and remain a significant issue in cloud security. With Cloud Security Posture Management (CSPM) tools available to counter cloud misconfigurations, their effectiveness, like their existence, is often unknown, misunderstood, or underutilised. This paper helps understand free tools, including both AWS and Azure first-party CSPMs and a third-party CSPM (Prowler), and assesses the effectiveness of an AI-generated DIY misconfiguration scanner in comparison to the Azure and AWS cloud environments. These tools were evaluated against 28 misconfigurations in the Azure environment and 24 equivalent misconfigurations in the AWS environment, including VMs, storage services, databases, and cloud identity platforms. With detection rates ranging from 7.1% to 78.6%, no tool met the 80% target; however, Prowler performed best across both environments, achieving 4 out of 8 severity-specific targets. The DIY scanner held the weakest overall performance of the three, whilst the first-party scanners had held satisfactory but poor performance between the DIY scanner and the third-party CSPM. While performances varied, the experiment highlights that CSPM tools can be useful, though they should not be relied on exclusively due to gaps in detection and over-sensitivity. Finally, concluding that CSPM tools can be an aid, though they should be combined with additional tools such as XDRs to help prevent security incidents. However, opportunities for additional future research remain open, due to the budget and time constraints imposed by this experiment.

Index Terms—Cloud Computing, Cybersecurity, Misconfiguration, Threats

1 INTRODUCTION

SINCE the introduction of Amazon Web Services (AWS) in 2006 as the first scalable and multi-service cloud platform, organisational infrastructure has shifted from traditional on-premises systems to more flexible cloud and hybrid environments (AWS n.d.b). This development introduced numerous new service models (SaaS, PaaS, IaaS), with each offering various levels of control and flexibility. It enables organisations to pay only for the resources needed, adjust their resource requirements dynamically on demand and shift data protection responsibilities. In modern times, 94% of organisations operate with cloud technologies (Colorlib 2025).

As with any technology, cloud platforms also introduce new threats, challenges, and risks. Primarily, these are enabled because of human factors. Humans, for example, aren't perfect; they're prone to errors, overlook security requirements, and are susceptible to manipulation. Luckily, cloud services such as Microsoft Azure and AWS are now starting to enforce MFA (Microsoft 2024, Schmidt 2024), countering some attacks enabled by weak and reused passwords (Toroman 2018, p. 293), including password spraying and social engineering.

1.1 The Persistent Threat of Cloud Misconfigurations

Among the threats enabled by human factors is the danger of cloud misconfigurations, which is becoming a rising problem in cloud security, with 23% of successful cloud security

incidents attributed to it (SentinelOne 2024). A single misconfiguration can lead to unauthorised access, internal sabotage, data exfiltration and more. All of which could have knock-on effects, resulting in fines, reputational damage, and operational issues. Whilst tools such as CSPMs exist to combat this threat, their actual effectiveness is not well understood. In an attempt to reduce misconfiguration-based cloud incidents, this research paper aims to answer the question "How well do third-party CSPM tools detect cloud misconfigurations?"

1.2 Aims, Objectives and Scope

This research aims to test the effectiveness of CSPM tools across two deliberately vulnerable cloud environments, specifically Azure and AWS, two of the top cloud service providers (one per). To assess such effectiveness, the study will measure the accuracy and coverage of these tools, examining their strengths and weaknesses in identifying misconfiguration-enabled threats. This will provide valuable insight into what each of the scanners does well and what they miss, in terms of correctly identified and unidentified misconfigurations.

Some additional limitations will impact the project's aims, objectives, and scope, primarily due to budget, time, and ethical constraints. For example, due to UK law and the ToS of cloud providers, ethical considerations partially restrict the scope of this research project, as testing must be conducted within permissible non-production environments that contain no organisational or user data. Consequently, if we do not do so, we lose the ability to test tools in actual environments

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and therefore lack fully 'production-tested' data. To combat some of these limitations, environments tested should mimic less enabled organisations, such as charities and non-profit organisations, but with potentially fewer cloud services due to budget constraints.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 What is the 'Cloud'?

The cloud is utilised by people, companies, and governments to store files reliably, host online services, and be accessible from anywhere in the world (Microsoft n.db). Services hosted in the cloud, away from on-premises environments, define the control over resources, such as IaaS, PaaS, and SaaS, as shown in Figure 1. Services can include websites (PaaS/SaaS), databases (PaaS), virtual machines (IaaS), and more. The type of service alone does not necessarily define its service model. However, today, organisations are likely to use all three types of cloud services, along with on-premises solutions.

Fig. 1: Cloud Service Models (Harvey 2018)

2.2 The Modern Cloud Landscape

2.2.1 Cloud Market Share

The cloud market share is dominated by three leading providers ("The Big Three"), including AWS, Azure and Google Cloud, collectively accounting for 63% of the cloud market share (see Figure 2). However, despite these tech giants' high market share, other providers are growing within the industry. Alibaba Cloud is a prime example of this, holding only 4% of the market share, but remains a leading provider in Asia, owned by the Chinese-owned giant, the Alibaba group (Haranas 2024). Other contenders in the overall market share include Oracle (3%), SaaS provider Salesforce (2%), IBM Cloud (2%) and Tencent Cloud (2%).

Organisations often use multiple cloud providers instead of relying on a single platform, and whilst it may seem unnecessary and more complex, it can sometimes be a more optimal approach. Single-cloud solutions offer simpler cloud administration, volume discounts, and easy integration with other cloud services. Still, they also pose the risk of being a single point of failure, even with redundancy-led configurations (Yeasmin et al. 2018). Multi-cloud instead offers better redundancy and access to a broader selection of cloud services, but may introduce unnecessary complexity to cloud infrastructure and higher OpEx.

Fig. 2: Cloud Market Share (Statista 2025)

2.2.2 Trends in Cloud Adoption

Instead of using exclusively cloud solutions, the use of on-premises infrastructure is common, especially in hybrid cloud environments, though on the decline. In 2023, 48% of IT workloads were reported to be hosted in corporate data centres away from the cloud, down from 58% in 2020 (Smolaks 2024). Despite this, on-premises infrastructure may still be preferred for some organisations, especially when sensitive data is handled (Anderson et al. 2023). As a result, top CSPs, including both Azure and AWS, have introduced sovereign zones for compliance, regulatory requirements and data residency (see Appendix A).

Research suggests that non-profits and charities are currently less likely to adopt the cloud and more likely to struggle to utilise it. According to an article on the adoption of technology, NGOs (including non-profits and charities) report having less access to digital infrastructure, expertise and funding (Godefroid et al. 2024). However, cloud usage amongst these groups is expected to increase, with 53% expecting to increase their cloud usage as cloud technology becomes more widespread. (Smith 2023)

2.3 The Basics of CSPM Tools

2.3.1 Defining Purpose

Security management in the cloud can be complex to maintain as the number of applications and services deployed to cloud environments (or 'tenants') increases. OAuth apps, firewalls, security groups, and more each contribute to the pile-up of permissions and rules, all of which can be misconfigured, leaving gaps that threat actors can leverage. One of the primary purposes of CSPM tools is to identify these misconfigurations, monitor compliance, and provide risk assessment management.

A variety of CSPM tools exist, each with different features, costs and levels of support for multi-cloud environments. Examples include first-party CSPMs such as Azure Defender CSPM and AWS Security Hub CSPM, as well as third-party CSPMs such as Prowler. Each service is billed differently, typically using a contractual pay-per-month model or a pay-per-resource model, with some even offering free options with less coverage or functionality. The growing complexity of cloud infrastructure has driven demand for these tools, with 52%

of organisations reportedly having complexity in their cloud infrastructure (Evans 2025). Reflectively, the CSPM market size is expected to reach \$10.37 billion by 2030, almost double the market size of 2024 (Grand View Research 2024).

2.3.2 CSPMs vs Alternative Tools

CSPM tools are among the various cloud security tools available to cloud administrators, alongside other tools such as CWPP and CIEM. The main difference between these tools is their coverage: CIEM covers IAM (e.g., Entra ID permissions), while CWP covers running workloads (e.g., VMs, functions). Whilst CSPM provides coverage for the entire environment configuration, another tool combines CSPM, CWPP, and CIEM to provide maximum coverage, known as a CNAPP. Whilst CNAPP tools like Wiz and Defender for Cloud look like the go-to products, they include high costs, with the Wiz median buyer paying \$145,562 per year (Vendr n.d).

In comparison to CSPM tools, which often have free plans available and seem to be more accessible, smaller organisations and charities may not have the funding to pay for all-in-one CNAPP tools. Research suggests that charities struggle to fund cybersecurity practices, with just 26% of charities in the UK reporting completion of a cybersecurity risk assessment (UK Government, DSIT 2024). Similarly, SMEs have also been reported to have difficulties with balancing financial troubles with best-practice security measures (Ejaz & Matthew 2024).

2.3.3 Existing Research on CSPM Effectiveness

CSPM tools have become a vital part of cloud security strategy; however, academic sources comparing these tools remain scarce. Despite a lack of sources, some do exist without going into a practical analysis of their effectiveness. For instance, a study by Sharma (2020) discusses strategies and challenges in implementing CSPMs, yet does not conduct practical tests to evaluate their effectiveness. While the study drew meaningful conclusions, this highlights a research gap and underscores the need for a comprehensive study to test the effectiveness of such tools.

An article published by Gandhi (2024) on the effectiveness of CSPMs highlights their ability to identify misconfigurations in multi-cloud environments. More specifically, it reports an industry effectiveness range between 87-94% when comparing the CSPM capabilities of AWS and Azure as first-party providers. However, whilst this research exists, it is based on secondary research, lacks an explicit definition of efficiency, fails to explain how metrics such as detection rate are derived, and does not include research into third-party tools. Without explicit self-conducted analysis, this paper highlights a research gap that it aims to address.

2.4 Misconfiguration- Enabled Cloud Security Incidents

Misconfigurations have contributed to some of the most significant cybersecurity incidents we have seen in recent years. Notably, in 2019, Capital One, a major U.S. bank, was hit by a massive data breach costing \$190,000,000 in settlements. The breach was caused by cloud misconfigurations, including an over-privileged IAM role and a misconfigured WAF that resulted in an SSRF vulnerability (Khan et al. 2022). These two human-made mistakes led to the sensitive data of over 100 million people being leaked, including credit card customer

data, bank account numbers, SSNs, and more (CapitalOne 2019). All of which was stored in AWS S3 buckets, to which the attacker was also able to access due to a lack of least privilege principle enforcement.

Furthermore, there has been an incident involving misconfigurations in Microsoft's own cloud tenant between late 2023 and early 2024, attributed to the Russian state actor group APT-29. Despite primarily using password spraying, the attack exploited a legacy OAuth application with elevated permissions, which was a cloud misconfiguration that enabled the attackers to gain escalated privileges (Metibemu et al. 2025). Whilst the attack did not result in fines or significant damage, it did result in stolen source code, data exfiltration, and reputational damage.

However, it's not only big organisations that are facing cyberattacks involving cloud misconfigurations; charities and small or non-profit organisations are also experiencing the same types of incidents resulting in data loss, compliance breaches, unauthorised access and more (Dawson 2025). Cybersecurity incidents, including these, rarely get reported (UK Government, DSIT 2024), which is why we don't often hear about them when they occur, suggesting a potential need for CSPM tools to support early intervention.

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Data Collection & Analysis Methods

To collect data, this project uses quantitative methods and tools to assess misconfigured cloud environments. Specifically, it intends to record and compare numerical outcomes (NU 2023), including accuracy scores, false-negative rates, and more, to show each tool's efficiency. Detecting cloud misconfigurations in this way makes it much more reproducible, yielding similar or identical results. In contrast, qualitative methods, such as surveys, may yield differing results depending on the audience completing them, with further risks towards bias.

Tools to detect cloud misconfigurations will produce very different results depending on the cloud environment, which is why an inductive analysis method will be used. In this sense, we can broadly take a grasp of effectiveness to discuss the CSPM's strengths and weaknesses, whilst also adapting to any unexpected findings that one or more of the tools might uncover. Deductive, on the other hand, could introduce bias from the beginning by starting with a theory (Salomão 2023), and may limit the project's flexibility.

3.2 Selected Environments and Tools

3.2.1 Cloud Environments

The three chosen tools will be tested in two similarly configured single-cloud environments, which cover two of the top cloud service providers: AWS and Azure. Whilst the project may benefit from a broader scope, with potentially Alibaba Cloud, Oracle or even Google Cloud, some considerations have led to the use of just AWS and Azure. Specifically, utilising these two top CSPs ensures we can maximise the benefits of this project, given budget and time constraints, while also enabling the research to capture 50% of the market share (Statista 2025). Therefore, by choosing these two CSPs, we

achieve broader coverage, making the research more beneficial to a larger number of people and organisations.

The two single-cloud environments will include 4-6 of the most common misconfigurations across six domains (Quist 2020): IAM, networking, storage, compute, monitoring, and compliance. Financial constraints have limited the scope of these misconfigurations to those included in the student plans for both AWS and Azure. However, the use of student plans still allows access to some of the most used cloud services, such as virtual machines and storage buckets/blobs. Each misconfiguration has an applicable severity, though they typically differ from organisation to organisation.

Fig. 4: Prowler Dashboard (Prowler n.d.)

Category	Misconfiguration (Azure)	Misconfiguration (AWS)	Severity
Identity and Access Management (IAM)	Overly Permissive RBAC role	Overly permissive RBAC role	Critical
Identity and Access Management (IAM)	No MFA Enforcement	No MFA Enforcement	Critical
Identity and Access Management (IAM)	Overly Permissive Guest Users	Overly Permissive Guest User	High
Identity and Access Management (IAM)	Excessive Subscription Owner Role Assignments	Excessive Admin Assignments	High
Networking and Firewall	DDoS protection standard disabled on VNets	AWS Shield Advanced not enabled	Medium
Networking and Firewall	Weak NSG Inbound Rules (Allow all inbound on NSG)	Weak NACL Inbound Rules (Allow all inbound on NSG)	Critical
Networking and Firewall	Management Ports Exposed via VM NSG (RDP/HTT)	Management Ports Exposed via VM Security Groups (SSH/HTT)	Critical
Networking and Firewall	Key Vault Public Network Access Enabled (No Firewall)	Secrets Manager Accessible Without Policy Restriction	Critical
Storage and Data Exposure	Storage and DB Resources Limited to US Redundancy	DB Resources Limited to Single-AZ (Storage Not Possible)	Medium
Storage and Data Exposure	Public Network Access for Blob Storage	Public Network Access for S3 Storage	Medium
Storage and Data Exposure	Soft Delete Disabled for Blob Storage	No Equivalent	Low
Storage and Data Exposure	Versioning Disabled for Blob Storage	Versioning Disabled for S3	Low
Storage and Data Exposure	Risk Infrastructure Encryption Disabled	No Equivalent	Medium
Storage and Data Exposure	MySQL Password Auth for database	Self Managed Password Auth for Database	Medium
Compute and VM	Vulnerability Assessment Extension Not Installed	AWS Inspector Not Enabled	High
Compute and VM	Management Ports Exposed via VM NSG (RDP/HTT)	Management Ports Exposed via VM Security Groups (SSH/HTT)	High
Compute and VM	No Disk Encryption on Host Windows VM	No Disk Encryption on Host EC2 Linux VM	Medium
Compute and VM	Hot Patch/Automatic OS Updates Disabled	No Patch Manager for Automatic Updates	Medium
Compute and VM	No Availability Zones on Windows VM	No Equivalent	Low
Monitoring and Logging	Log Analytics Retention Below 30 days	CloudWatch Logs Retention Below 30 days	Low
Monitoring and Logging	VNet Flow Logs Disabled	No Created VPC Flow Logs	Low
Monitoring and Logging	No Key Vault Diagnostic Logs	No Secrets Manager CloudTrail Logs	Low
Monitoring and Logging	No Contact Email for Security Issues	No Contact Email for Security Issues	High
Compliance and Governance	Backup Retention Below 30 days (VM)	AWS Backup Retention Below 30 days (VM)	High
Compliance and Governance	Deprecated Database Versions in Use	No Equivalent	Low
Compliance and Governance	Resource Tags Missing	Resource Tags Missing	Medium
Compliance and Governance	No Resource Locks	No IAM Deny Policies / Deletion Prevention Disabled	Medium
Compliance and Governance	No Backup Policies	No AWS Backup Plans	Medium

Fig. 3: Pre-constructed List of Misconfigurations

3.2.2 Tool Selection

As shown in Figure ??, three types of tools have been selected for direct comparison across the two cloud environments; each has been strategically chosen to ensure a fair test while providing a good level of coverage. This is particularly important as some organisations operate with multiple CSPs, whilst others may stick to a single one. However, it is worth noting that each tool has been selected as it is free due to budget constraints, which may impact the scope of results that can be obtained. Tools chosen include first-party CSPMs for both Azure (Microsoft n.d.a) and AWS (n.d.a), Prowler as a third-party CSPM compatible with both cloud providers, and a DIY misconfiguration scanner (not classed as a full CSPM).

TABLE 1: Tool Selection Table

Tool Used	Azure	AWS
Built-in CSPMs (Free)	Defender for Cloud (Foundational CSPM)	AWS Security Hub CSPM
Prowler CSPM	Prowler CSPM	Prowler CSPM
DIY Scanner	PowerShell via Azure CLI	Python via AWS CLI

Each tool is deployed and used in its own way. For built-in 'first-party' CSPMs, these are integrated within their respective cloud portals and can be accessed with a few button clicks, such as in the Defender for Cloud dashboard. Third-party CSPM Prowler and the DIY scanner, however, require additional setup, with third-party tools like Prowler requiring Docker and access keys or CLI tokens. The prowler dashboard can be seen in Figure 4.

As creating a DIY scanner whilst knowing the exact misconfigurations would risk an unfair test, the DIY scanner has been created with ChatGPT (2025) and is contained in Appendix B. In modern times, this reflects how AI is used today, with 88% of organisations using AI (Naik 2025) for automation, cybersecurity, and much more. Therefore, an AI-created solution for a scanner is highly realistic. Additionally, the DIY scanner involves the use of Azure or AWS CLI, as shown in Figure 5.

Fig. 5: DIY Scanner Execution

3.3 Metrics and Targets

Based on a published article on the effectiveness of CSPMs, industry performance in identifying configuration and privilege issues is reported as ranging from 87% to 94% (Gandhi 2024). The tools tested aim to meet targets before they can be deemed 'effective' across three specific metrics: detection rate, cross-cloud consistency, and severity effectiveness rate. Targets defined are reflected by this published article, with consideration that performance may not be entirely accurate.

3.3.1 Detection Rate (Accuracy)

Detection Rate is a metric that measures the tool's ability to correctly identify all misconfigurations in the cloud environment, reflecting True Positives (TP) and False Negatives (FN), expressed as a percentage (Google 2025). The target detection rate for each tool is 80%, slightly undercutting the minimum of the industry effectiveness range outlined in an article from Gandhi (2024).

$$Detection\ Rate = \frac{Correct\ Detections}{Total\ Misconfigurations} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Target: 80%

3.3.2 Cross Cloud Consistency

Cross-cloud consistency measures how well a tool category (e.g. Prowler or DIY Scanner) performs in both cloud environments. The target for cross-cloud consistency is set to 75%, due to expected differences in tool performance across environments, with Azure reportedly showing 3-6% lower accuracy and coverage than AWS (Gandhi 2024).

$$Cross\ Cloud\ Consistency = \frac{AWS + Azure\ Detected}{AWS + Azure\ Misconfigurations} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

Target: 75%

3.3.3 Severity Effectiveness Rate

Severity effectiveness rate shows how well a tool performed in identifying misconfigurations in a particular category of severity. The target for severity effectiveness is set as a range rather than a fixed percentage (70-90%), reflecting the importance of detecting the majority of high and critical-level misconfigurations (Laderman et al. 2024) over low and medium-level misconfigurations (Gandhi 2024).

$$Severity\ Effectiveness\ Rate = \frac{Detected\ (Severity)}{Total\ (Severity)} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

Target: 70-90%:

- Low: 70%
- Medium: 75%
- High: 80%
- Critical: 90%

3.3.4 Error

The absolute error measures how well the tools detect the intended misconfigurations, accounting for both detection sensitivity and the total number of detections.

$$Error = |Actual - Detected| \quad (4)$$

Whilst there is no set target for this metric due to a lack of existing error data, a perfect error would be 0, with higher values indicating potentially too high sensitivity, a low number of detections, duplicate detections, or recommendations for products like Defender for IoT or AWS Security Hub extensions. A low or perfect error rate does not necessarily mean that the tool is good, as a tool could make the same number of detections as the actual, but get them wrong; however, it can indicate performance. As the error is an absolute value, it cannot be negative.

4 RESULTS & DISCUSSION

4.1 Metrical Scores & Target Comparison

As shown in Figure 6, the difference in detection rate per model is clear, with overall performance ranging from 7.1% to 78.6%, indicating that the percentage of False Negatives (FNs) ranges between 21.4% and 92.9%. Results from this figure suggest that the previously set target of an 80% detection rate has not been met, despite Prowler holding closely behind in both AWS and Azure environments.

Despite none of the three tools reaching the target, the performance of each tool across the six distinct categories is visible in the line graphs shown in Figure 7. In which prowlter meets targets in specific domains, such as IAM, Storage,

Fig. 6: Detection Rate Bar Chart

Networking and Compliance for Azure, as well as Compliance for AWS. Both first-party tools also come close to the preset 80% detection rate target, with top scores of 75% for both Azure and AWS provided CSPMs across different categories. However, achieving a higher score in some categories becomes nearly impossible due to the low number of misconfigurations in specific domains, particularly those with only 4 misconfigurations, requiring all misconfigurations to be identified for a passing score.

Fig. 7: Domain Specific Performances

The consistency of tools across the two cloud environments essentially shows how consistently a tool performs across multiple cloud environments. Whilst not as useful a metric for this study, where we are only testing tools against two cloud environments, further extensions or future research on this topic can utilise this metric more appropriately. Further highlighted in Figure 8, the results are similar to those of the detection rate bar chart. Despite the first-party CSPM and DIY scanner being far away from the target of 75%, Prowler has been the most consistent tool for detecting misconfigurations in both environments. Suggesting that potentially, both third-party scanners look for the same misconfigurations in the two environments.

Fig. 8: Cross-Cloud Consistency Comparison

However, a final metric that captures each tool's overall effectiveness is the severity effectiveness rate, which varies by

a tool’s ability to detect misconfigurations at a given severity level (see Figure 9). These results highlight that the most consistent tool for detecting all types of misconfigurations in the Azure environment has been Prowler, achieving 3/4 of the severity-targeted detections. The only other tool that came close to this was Prowler again in the AWS environment, though it still reached only one of the four targets. The performance of first-party tools is similar, particularly in detecting higher-severity misconfigurations. However, neither meets targets, as is also the case with the DIY scanners, which have the weakest overall performance.

Fig. 9: Severity Detection Heatmap

4.2 Uncertainties of Results

4.2.1 Deviations and Anomalies

Both the deviations and anomalies identified provide insight into unexpected patterns or behaviour in CSPM tools, issues with data quality, and other potential errors or interesting changes within data. Often, these can be caused by a system or human error, or by an external factor; however, they can also be genuine and mistake-free (Metaplane 2025). During the analysis of results, several deviations and anomalies became apparent, primarily stemming from methodological constraints rather than direct errors during the experimental process.

Whilst the existing literature reports detection effectiveness ranging from 87% to 94%, results from this study reported far lower effectiveness, with the highest detection rate being 78.6%. Results conducted do not reach even the lower percentage of the reported detection effectiveness range. Though likely due to a lower number of created misconfigurations, this was reflected in the set targets, which all tools failed to meet overall, though they may have met them in detecting particular categories of severity or domains.

Additionally, even with the top-scoring tool (Prowler) in both Azure and AWS environments, Prowler also held the second-highest error rate for AWS, behind the AWS first-party CSPM (see Figure 10), just over six times more than Azure Prowler. This essentially means that while the tool did detect a majority of the misconfigurations, the number of detections required to do so was 228, far greater than the 24 implemented for the AWS environment, resulting in a 204 error rate. However, Prowler (AWS) is not alone; the first-party scanner has also detected a significant number of issues, potentially suggesting that unintended misconfigurations may have been introduced to the environment during the experimental process.

Fig. 10: Error by Tool and Cloud

4.2.2 Limitations of Final Results

The results contained in this study have come from redundant services, without assigned use cases or data storage. Whilst constraints have limited the setup, a lack of replication could have affected the results, potentially leading to more or fewer detected misconfigurations. Importantly, for different organisations, what may be classed as a misconfiguration in this study may be an intended configuration. Typically, misconfigurations, like any risk, need to be reviewed with their own class of severity, depending on the context, and organisations may have to decide how to prioritise and eliminate risk based on these suggestions, and use risk to measure the likelihood and impact (Laderman et al. 2024, p. 20)

Additionally, given time constraints, this research covered a broad scope, using three different tools and replicating up to 28 misconfigurations across the two environments. Essentially, whilst only three types of tools had been used, five different tools were actually used, with the same cross-compatible tool ‘Prowler’ used in both environments. Whilst this project aimed to maintain breadth, it may have missed out on depth, thereby limiting the potential to achieve more effective results with fewer tools and fewer misconfigurations.

4.3 Implications for Security Practice

Results from this study highlight the options organisations have when reviewing their security posture and that CSPMs can be capable tools, especially compared to basic tools created in-house or by AI. However, even with CSPM capabilities and a detection rate of 78.6%, they are much more effective when paired with additional security tools and penetration testing, allowing previously unidentified gaps to be filled and future attack attempts to be prevented. SIEM tools are a great example of this, with integration with platforms like Sentinel and Splunk to identify network events (Cymulate n.d.).

5 CONCLUSION

In conclusion, whilst Prowler dominated across all categories in both the Azure and AWS environments, the question of whether CSPM tools should be relied on exclusively holds a clear answer. With imperfect peak detection rates of 75-78.6%, third-party tools have proven more effective than free first-party or homemade tools. Still, they have gaps and errors, making them far from perfect and far from industry claims (Gandhi 2024).

Despite varying performances, all tools tested may benefit from further development, testing, and optimisation to improve their ability to detect cloud misconfigurations. Interestingly, results showed that the strongest-performing tools

produced a high number of errors, whilst DIY and first-party tools generally performed poorly when detecting the implemented misconfigurations. Whilst potentially manageable for some, this becomes an added challenge for some organisations, with either too many detections and significant analytical overhead or not enough detections to patch all threats in cloud environments.

This study also highlights the potential for additional future research in the area, due to constraints imposed by budget and time, which led to the use of non-premium CSPM tools in two non-production environments. Ideally, this experiment would have been better off if conducted across more than two organisational environments. Potentially resulting in more data and a broader, more complete view of detection rates, cross-cloud consistency, and the effectiveness of severity ratings for both free and paid tools.

Nonetheless, this research highlights how far low-funded organisations can go with no-cost CSPM tools to improve their cloud cybersecurity posture for essential services, demonstrating the potential value of such tools. Particularly important in countering misconfigurations across essential cloud services such as VMs, storage buckets, databases, and IAM platforms. Concluding that CSPMs can be effective, but may need to be paired with appropriate risk management and additional security tools, such as XDRs, to prevent security incidents (ANSecurity 2025).

APPENDIX A SOVEREIGN CLOUD

The emergence of sovereign cloud dates back to the introduction of the GAIA-X initiative in 2019, which aimed to address the challenges faced by non-European CSPs when dealing with European customers and requirements (Johnson 2021). This was to ensure data sovereignty and compliance with European regulations, including the General Data Protection Regulations of 2018. This development influenced cloud providers, including 'The Big Three' (Amazon Web Services, Google Cloud and Microsoft Azure), to now offer what is known as sovereign zones to help ensure compliance without requiring strictly air-gapped instances.

Sovereign Zones are an aid when creating a brand new cloud environment; any administrator with the relevant permissions can set up their cloud environment based on a template, otherwise known as a 'Landing Zone'. However, Sovereign Landing Zones go beyond that, preparing cloud environments with a suitable foundation for data sovereignty.

APPENDIX B DIY SCANNER

Using ChatGPT (2025), a DIY scanner has been created for both Azure and AWS. This includes one PowerShell script to be used in Azure, and one Python script to be used in AWS.

The scripts/codes are available via: <https://aiarchives.org/id/a2y4STv3OSRtwXwwQWsS>

APPENDIX C LIST OF ACRONYMS

AWS	Amazon Web Services
CSP	Cloud Service Provider
CIEM	Cloud Infrastructure Entitlement Management
CNAPP	Cloud-Native Application Protection Platform
CLI	Command Line Interface
CSPM	Cloud Security Posture Management
CWPP	Cloud Workflow Protection Platform
DIY	Do It Yourself
FN	False Negative
IaaS	Infrastructure as a Service
IAM	Identity and Access Management
MFA	Multi-Factor Authentication
NGO	Non-Government Organisation
OpEx	Operational Expenditure
PaaS	Platform as a Service
S3	Simple Storage Service
SaaS	Software as a Service
SSRF	Server-Side Request Forgery
ToS	Terms of Service
TP	True Positive
WAF	Web Application Firewall

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